

**Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids from the Stand-
point of Smoluchowski's Theory. Part I.
Coagulation of Antimony Sulphide Sol.**

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The applicability of Smoluchowski's theory (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, **92**, 129) has been considered by most of the earlier workers with respect to the equation,

$$\sum n = n_0 / (1 + \beta t), \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where n_0 denotes the original number of primaries and β the velocity constant. $\sum n$ gives the total number of particles in all stages of coalescence at the time t . The object of the present work was to examine another general result (*cf.* Anderson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, **19**, 623; also Freundlich and Basu, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **115**, 203) of the above theory,

viz.,
$$\beta = \frac{1}{t} [\sqrt{n_0/n_t} - 1] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where n_t is the number of primaries in the coagulating sol at the time t .

EXPERIMENTAL.

The colloid was prepared by adding intermittently and with constant shaking a solution of tartar emetic to a large volume of twice-distilled water, saturated with hydrogen sulphide. The sol was much more stable than that obtained by leading H_2S in tartar emetic solution. This was found to be due to the precipitating action of small quantities of free antimonious acid produced in the latter case. After dialysing till free from acid, the sol was filtered and stocked in carefully cleaned and well stoppered hard-glass bottles. The colloid-content of the sol was determined by Kessler's method (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1863, **118**, 17). After the sol, the coagulator solution ($N/10-H_2SO_4$) and the reaction vessel had attained the thermostat

temperature, 25 c.c. of the coagulator solution were introduced simultaneously from two similar pipettes into the reaction vessel. After a definite time, the mixture was filtered, using a high grade analytical filter paper and the precipitate was washed with 20 c.c. of water. The time required for pipetting the solution in (7 sec.) and that for washing the precipitate (30 sec.) could be made practically constant. In these results a , $a-x$ denote respectively the colloid-content of the original sol and that of the coagulating sol at any time t , during coagulation. t , is exclusive of the time required for pipetting in and for washing the precipitate.

k , the bi-molecular constant and β , the Smoluchowski's constant were calculated from the values of $a-x$ read off from the curve A in fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

Same axes { Curve A, variation of $(a-x)$ with time.
Curve B, ,, ,, x with temperature.

Influence of temperature on percentage of coagulation was studied in three series of experiments, the time (5 and 1.5 min.) being kept constant in each series (Table II and curve B in fig. 1). Viscosity of the coagulating sol was determined at different temperatures using an Ostwald's viscometer, 3, 5 and 7 min. after the start of coagulation. The corresponding densities were measured by means of a standard specific gravity bottle. The viscosity recorded in Table III represents mean of three independent readings.

TABLE I.

Temp. = 33°.

Initial colloid concentration = 0.124 g. Sb_2S_3 per litre.10 c.c. FeSO_4 soln. = 0.01411 g. Sb_2S_3 .

Time (min.).	Titre value for filtrate (c.c.).	($a-x$) in 50 c.c. of the mixture.	$a-x/a$	k	B
0	4.4	0.00621 (a)*			
1	3.1	0.00438	0.705	0.52	0.126
2	2.25	0.00318	0.512	0.45	0.18
3	2.0	0.00282	0.454	0.39	0.113
4	2.1	0.00296	0.477	0.32	0.124
5	1.9	0.00268	0.432	0.26	0.103
7	1.75	0.00247	0.398	0.22	0.09

TABLE II.

A.

Time of coagulation = 5 min.

0.27g. of Sb_2S_3 per litre. 10 c.c. of FeSO_4 soln. = 0.01547 g. Sb_2S_3 .

Temp.	Titre (c.c.)	($a-x$) in 50 c.c. of mixture.	Percentage coagulation.
	4.1	0.00634 (a)*	—
34°	1.95	0.00302	52.4
„	1.95	0.00302	52.4
50°	1.55	0.00239	52.3
„	1.55	0.00239	62.3
70°	1.05	0.00162	74.4
	1.2	0.00185	70.7

B.

Time of coagulation = 1.5 min.

0.135g. of Sb_2S_3 per litre. 10 c. c. of FeSO_4 soln. = 0.0547g. Sb_2S_3 .

Temp.	Titre (c.c.)	($a-x$) in 50 c.c. of mixture.	Percentage coagulation.
	4.4	0.00680(a)*	—
	4.35	0.00673(a)*	—
34°	2.3	0.00354	47.8
„	2.25	0.00348	48.6
54°	2.15	0.03329	53.1
„	2.05	0.00317	51.3

C. (cf. curve B, Fig. 1.)

Time of coagulation = 5.0 min. 0.2436 g. of Sb_2S_3 per litre.

0°	0.00328	46.2
14°.5	0.00312	48.9
23°.5	0.00339	44.4
34°	0.00273	55.1
50°	0.00266	55.4
59°	0.00242	60.3
68°	0.00180	70.5

* a = Initial colloid-content.

TABLE III-

Temp.	x/a from fig. 1,		Viscosity of water. η_w	Viscosity of colloid. η	Ratio, $\beta_T / \beta_{33.5}$		
	curve B.	β			with η_w	with η	observed,
33°.5	0.52	0.0886	0.0072	0.00743	1.0	1.0	1.0
43°.5	0.54	0.0946	0.0062	0.00638	1.25	1.20	1.07
53°.5	0.57	0.105	0.00515	0.00574	1.55	1.39	1.18
62°	0.64	0.133	0.00458	0.00538	1.79	1.51	1.50
73°	0.75	0.2	0.0039	0.00484	2.17	1.73	2.26

Discussion of Results.

In applying equation (1) in general, the assumption is necessarily implied that a property like viscosity (Miyazawa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1912, 33, 1179 ; Freundlich and Ishizaka, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1913, 9, 66 ; Gann, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1916, 8, 65), or, relative transparency (Mukherjee and Majumdar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 794 ; Desai, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 19, 181), is a single-valued function of $\sum n$. Since coalescence of particles is the chief effect in coagulation, its progress is best followed by employing a property depending upon the particle size. Thus Paine (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1912, 4, 24) determined $a-x$, the uncoagulated part of a copper sol by separating the coagulum by stirring. In later work (Paine and Evans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 24, 649) a sample of the coagulating sol was heated quickly (which precipitated the coagulum), and a portion drawn off to measure $a-x$. Each of these methods is subject to an indeterminate correction, on account of the assumption regarding $\sum n$ mentioned above. Whilst this would appear to be inevitable, especially in the case of polydisperse colloids, it is advantageous to examine the theory, using different methods of determining coagulation. This has been in progress for some time in these laboratories. The chief condition to be satisfied in employing any given property for measuring coagulation is that it shall vary continuously during coagulation without turning points. This is seen to be the case from curve A in Fig. 1. The amount of the coagulum determined at a given time during coagulation is therefore characteristic of the corresponding state of coagulation. Data given in Table II show that the degree of reproducibility of results for $a-x$ at different temperatures and for short intervals of time is good. Denoting by n_t , r , and ρ the number, the mean radius, and the density of the primaries at a time t , we get, $a-x = 4/3\pi\rho(r_1^3n_t + r'^3n')$, where r' and n' refer to particles in a higher state of coalescence. r'^3n' is determined chiefly by the texture of the filter paper used. It is a measure of the average volume of particles at higher stages of coalescence. The number of particles at higher stages of coagulation has been assumed to be negligible as a first approximation. $a/a-x$ therefore, equals n_0/n_t involved in equation (2). More detailed results indicating the applicability of this method of measuring coagulation to other coagulating systems will be published shortly.

In Smoluchowski's theory, it is shown that the coagulation rate

exceeds that corresponding to a bimolecular reaction. It follows therefore, that in general, k , the bimolecular constant should increase with time in both rapid and slow coagulation. The results in Table I show just the opposite. Similar results were obtained by Anderson (*loc. cit.*) in the slow coagulation of gold sol. It is also seen from results in Table I that the constant β diminishes during coagulation. It is known in general, that the diminution of β with time is greater, slower the coagulation. In typical slow coagulation, β falls to a small fraction of the initial value soon after the start of coagulation. The observed decrease in β (about 20%) while 30% of the colloid has coagulated, shows that the rate is intermediate between the rapid and slow coagulations (*cf.* also Anderson, *loc. cit.*).

Results in Tables II, III (*cf.* also curve B, Fig. 1) show that the influence of temperature is more marked in the coagulation of the antimony sulphide than in that of the arsenious sulphide sol (Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 350). As regards the general influence of temperature on β , deducible from Smoluchowski's theory, Westgren and Keitstötter (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, 92, 750) have

shown that $\beta = \frac{RT}{N} \cdot \frac{n_0}{n_t}$ (3), where the different symbols have their usual significance. It follows therefore that $\beta_{T_1}/\beta_T = T/T_1$.

η_1/η (4) The results for this ratio given in Table III show that the agreement between theory and observation is but limited. The discrepancy between the two sets of values tends to diminish, when the viscosity of the colloid instead of that of water, is employed in calculating the ratio. In these results β contains implicitly the factor ϵ , which Smoluchowski employed to differentiate slow from rapid coagulation. ϵ denotes the probability of coalescence in a collision between two particles in the coagulating sol. It depends upon the surface density of the electrical charge on the particle and would diminish due to coalescence (Anderson, *loc. cit.*) producing a like variation in β (*cf.* Table I). The derivation of (4) from (3) necessitates that ϵ is independent of temperature. This is seen from the results of Freundlich and Basu (*loc. cit.*) and of Garner and Lewis (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1401), who observed that equation (4) was applicable. It is however doubtful, if this can be in general true. It is more probable that the temperature variation of ϵ depends upon the chemical nature of the sol. Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1563) observed that ϵ might vary with

temperature due to its influence on the ionic adsorption, which determines the charge on the colloid particle. The difference between the observed and calculated values of the ratio β_T / β_{T_1} might be ascribed therefore in part to the above possibility.

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